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STRATEGIC ALLIANCES: SUCCESS SUTRA FOR MODERN CORPORATIONS

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ABSTRACT

As strategic alliances are becoming an attractive component of success strategy for the modern organizations, they are gaining popularity day by day. This paper examines the literature on strategic alliances. The paper examines two theoretical models of strategic alliances, suggested by Vyas et al. and Osland and Yaprak along with the integrated model proposed by Sameer Vaidya. This paper also investigates literature concerning advantages and disadvantages of entering into a strategic alliance.

INTRODUCTION

A strategic alliance is a business arrangement in which two or more firms cooperate for their mutual benefit. Firms may combine their efforts for a variety of purposes including, but not limited to, sharing knowledge, expertise, and expenses as well as to gain entry to new markets or to gain a competitive advantage. Further, creation of a strategic alliance may turn actual or potential competitors into partners working toward a common goal. Use of strategic alliances has become a major tool for businesses that are internationalizing their operations. Due to the maturation of several trends of the 1980s, such as: intensified foreign competition, shortened product life cycles, soaring cost of capital, including the cost of research and development, and ever-growing demand for new technologies, alliances are becoming an attractive strategy for the future. Therefore, use of strategic alliances has expanded dramatically over the past decade, and their use will continue to increase as we go deeper into 21st century

Strategic alliances can be placed on a continuum where contractual agreements lie on one end of the continuum, representing low control and low resource commitment, whereas

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joint ventures lie on the other end of the continuum, representing high control and high resource commitment. The decision to enter a strategic alliance should be taken seriously by management because history has shown that alliances tend to be unstable and prone to failure. Firms that enter into strategic alliances often focus on the benefits that the alliances will provide without considering costs involved in the formation and maintenance of the alliance. Despite the clear identification of the potential benefits, the

costs incurred are often both substantial and often difficult to predict.

Strategic alliances can cause major problems if not handled properly. They may fail because of many reasons. Failures in strategic alliances in addition to the increase in the number of alliances in the 70s have necessitated research in this area. Researchers as well as practitioners have conducted research in hopes of discovering relationships and linkages, which will facilitate successful domestic and international strategic alliances.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the literature in strategic alliances in order to identify models that specify relationships between strategic alliance formation and success. This paper intends to examine the motives for formation of strategic alliances as mentioned by different management academicians. Some of the conceptual models of strategic alliances will be presented and discussed along with the discussion of the benefits and limitations of entering into strategic alliances.

Before reviewing the literature in strategic alliances it is important to define strategic alliances. Parkhe defines strategic alliances as "relatively enduring interfirm cooperative arrangements, involving flows and linkages that use resources and/or governance structures from autonomous organizations, for the joint accomplishment of individual goals linked to the corporate mission of each sponsoring firm". Jarillo defines strategic alliances as "Long-term purposeful arrangements among distinct but related organizations that allow those firms to gain or sustain competitive advantage." Varadarajan and Cunningham define strategic alliances as "the pooling of specific resources and skills by the cooperating organizations in order to achieve common goals, as well as goals specific to the individual partners".

There has been a significant growth in the number of strategic alliances recently which has resulted in increasing interest in this field. The following sections will attempt to examine the literature and integrate the findings of researchers.

Theories Explaining Strategic Alliance

Three principal theories used to explain strategic alliances, are transaction cost economics, organization theory and business strategy as mentioned by Kogut. Transaction cost economics was developed by Williamson, who suggested that firms chose alternative arrangements that minimize the sum of production and transaction costs. According to Kogut, "transaction costs refer to the expenses

incurred for writing and enforcing contracts, for haggling over terms and contingent claims, for deviating from optimal kinds of investments in order to increase dependence on party or stabilize a relationship, and for administering a transaction". Transaction cost theory predicts that strategic alliances are designed to achieve such a minimum cost arrangement. However the strategy to form an alliance is always not just reactive such as cost reduction or internationalization etc, it is also proactive in that it creates new products, new markets, new organizations, new management techniques, and new technology.

The second approach suggested by Kogut was the organization theory approach, specifically the resource dependency. The resource dependence approach posits that organizations depend on other organizations within their environment to acquire needed resources. The formation of joint ventures is a means for stabilizing the flow of resources that a company needs and for reducing the uncertainty confronted by the company. The third approach to strategic alliances deals with competitive strategies of firms. Porter stated that the formation of strategic alliances depends on the five forces; the threat of new entrants, the bargaining power of suppliers, the bargaining power of buyers, the threat of substitute products, and rivalry among firms. The three generic strategies provided by Porter, cost leadership, product differentiation, and focus, are used in conjunction with the five forces in order to outperform competitors. The competitive strategies approach states that

alliances are formed also as a defensive mechanism in order to hedge against strategic uncertainty.

Researchers suggest that the three conceptual frameworks (transaction cost approach, the organization theory approach, and the competitive strategy approach) mentioned above should be considered as complements, rather than as rivals.

Motives for entering into strategic alliances:

Although primary motives to enter into an alliance is growth revenue or profit. In the literature following motives has been highlighted for formation of strategic alliances:

Market entry in the international arena: Due to increase in global competition, firms tend to enter foreign markets in order to improve their profitability as well as their market share. Strategic alliances benefit firms that seek complementary resources in a foreign partner.

Evade barriers to enter new international markets: New international markets, especially markets of developing countries, are often difficult to enter due to government regulations regarding full ownership of a subsidiary. Strategic alliances can be helpful in circumventing these barriers to enter new international markets.

Protection of the home market competitive position: By entering international markets through alliances, firms force foreign competitors at home divert their resources away

from expansion into the international markets, thus protecting the home market.

Broaden product line/fill product line gaps: Firms often enter alliances to increase the product line or fill gaps in the existing product line. Lack of technology or high cost of production may force a firm to seek a foreign partner to fill their product lines.

Enter new-product market domains: Firms that operate in stagnant or mature industries often enter alliances to gain a foothold in emerging industries.

Reduce potential of future competition: By entering into an alliance with another organization, firms tend to reduce future competition potential of that organization.

Raise entry barriers: Raising entry barriers by joining forces with other organizations is a powerful motive to enter into alliances. However, firms have to be careful not to violate the anti-

trust laws of either domestic or host country.
Enhance resource use efficiency: Alliances allow firms to lower their manufacturing costs, achieve efficiencies in the production process, and allow them to gain efficiency.

Resource extension: Firms that lack the resources to grow enter into strategic alliances. Small firms often enter into alliances in order to acquire R&D resources, which could be capital or efficiency.

Acquire new skills: Knowledge acquisition is an important element in formation of alliances. Partners in an alliance often attempt to learn as much as possible from the other partner while guarding their distinctive skills.

The motives discussed above can be classified under the three approaches defined by Kogut. Following table lists the motives and their classification in one of the three approaches.

Classification in one of the level approaches					
Transaction Approach	Cost	Organization Approach	Theory	Competitive Approach	Position
Enhance resource use efficiency		Acquire new skills		Entry into new markets	
Resource extension		Entry into new product market domains		Circumvent barriers to enter new markets	
				Protect competitive position in home market	
				Broaden product lines/fill gaps	
				Entry into new markets	
				Reduce threat of future competition	
				Raise entry barriers	

There are two forms of strategic alliances; market related and technology related. For firms in a mature industry, market related strategic alliances tend to be more profitable, whereas technology related strategic alliances tend to benefit firms in high technology industries relatively more than firms in mature industries. The need to innovate is more immediate in the high-tech industries and therefore the need to form an alliance in order to create innovative products and services is evident.

Stages of Alliance Formation:

A typical strategic alliance formation process involves these steps:

- **Alliance Need:** Feeling the need to form an alliance involves identifying the gap that exists between what the organization is and what it wants to be over a period of time.
- **Strategy Development:** Strategy development involves studying the alliance's feasibility, objectives and rationale, focusing on the major issues and challenges and development of resource strategies for production, technology, and people. It requires aligning alliance objectives with the overall corporate strategy.
- **Partner Assessment:** Partner assessment involves analyzing a potential partner's strengths and weaknesses, creating strategies for accommodating all partners' management styles, preparing appropriate partner selection criteria, understanding a partner's motives for joining the alliance and addressing resource capability gaps that may exist for a partner.
- **Contract Negotiation:** Contract negotiations

involves determining whether all parties have realistic objectives, forming high calibre negotiating teams, defining each partner's contributions and rewards as well as protect any proprietary information, addressing termination clauses, penalties for poor performance, and highlighting the degree to which arbitration procedures are clearly stated and understood.

- **Alliance Operation:** Alliance operations involves addressing senior management's commitment, finding the calibre of resources devoted to the alliance, linking of budgets and resources with strategic priorities, measuring and rewarding alliance performance, and assessing the performance and results of the alliance.
- **Alliance Termination:** Alliance termination involves winding down the alliance, for instance when its objectives have been met or cannot be met, or when a partner adjusts priorities or re-allocated resources elsewhere.

Models of Strategic Alliances:

Vyas et al. proposed a model of strategic alliances. The model states that a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis of the parent company should be conducted first in order to assess the need to form a strategic alliance. If a need is established, then a SWOT analysis of the group with alliance potential (GWAP) has to be conducted in order to examine the possibility of an alliance.

Vyas et al. posited that the four issues identified in the model are critical for the success of the alliance. The authors state that without goal

compatibility the partners will eventually pull in different directions and cause the alliance to fail. Synergy among the partners is necessary in order to achieve the task efficiently and effectively. A clear understanding of the value that a particular firm brings to the alliance along with a balanced contribution to the alliance will ensure the success of the alliance. Alliances in which one partner contributes more than the other tend to end as takeovers by the dominant partner.

The second model of strategic alliances presented here is proposed by Osland and Yaprak. This model suggested that organizations have strategic goals, which at times are not realistic by the organization's standards. The perceived "desired" state of goals and actual goals has a strategic gap, which can be closed by forming an alliance with other companies. The strategic gap can be expressed as "a gap between what they would like to achieve and what they are able to achieve". In this case, the motive for forming the strategic alliance is to reduce the perceived gap.

The size of the strategic gap imposes pressure on the firm to take action in order to reduce the gap. "The greater the size of the gap and the perceived importance of filling it, the more likely the firm will desire to form an alliance with another firm". The authors classify the needs of the firm using the resource dependency model:

1. Market power: market access and economies of scope
2. Efficiency: financial resources and

economies of scale

3. Competencies: Knowledge and skills in value added activities of the firm

Market power can be achieved by developing new markets for present products, developing new products for present markets, and entering new product-market domains. Alliance formation allows companies to achieve market power, in case they do not possess the capability to achieve those results. Efficiency is important, especially for the high-technology industries. Forming alliances allows firms to gain access to resources that make them more efficient. Alliances with large firms are particularly beneficial to smaller firms that lack resources to invest in R&D and new product development. Competencies, the third need in the strategic gap framework, relate to the organizational learning process. Firms use alliances to gain access to other firms' capabilities and attempt to build their knowledge base with their partner's information. Organizational knowledge provides firms with a competitive advantage and is therefore critical to the survival of the firm. Such knowledge creation often results in increasing the longevity of such alliances. However, organizational climate plays a big role in the creation of knowledge. The organizational climate of the firms in the alliance should facilitate the effective implementation and utilization of the knowledge.

The model suggested by Osland and Yaprak states that firms need to form alliances when they realize that there is a gap between their strategic goals and current goals. Alliance with

other firms will allow an organization to enhance their market power, increase their efficiency, or lower their costs. As the organizations work with each other, they develop trust in one another and strengthen the relationship which leads to the achievement of their goals.

In order to better understand the formation process of strategic alliances, Sameer Vaidya, presented an integrated framework by combining the models given by Vetat and Osland and Yaprak. Both began their model with the environmental analysis. The need to change is perceived after the firm scans the internal and the external environment in order to assess the current performance of the firm. The model suggested posits that the alliance formation process begins with the motives for formation of alliance. The motives for forming the alliance are considered to be the antecedent variables, which are derived from the literature. The internal and external environment plays an important role in the assessment of the motives for alliance formation. The need to form an alliance is perceived by management after the environmental analysis and identifying the needs of the firm that are not being fulfilled with current capabilities.

Selecting the right partner is very important to the success of the alliance. We have already discussed the importance of mutual commitment, change-oriented management on both sides, and ability to manage contrast cultures (corporate or national). The model divides strategic alliances into two parts: joint ventures and contractual agreements, which

include licensing, technology agreements, and supplier arrangements. The partner selection process for joint ventures and for contractual agreements includes a careful assessment of the bargaining power of each partner, control issues, trust and commitment issues, knowledge transfer issues, stability of the alliance, conflict resolution, and experience of the partners.

After carefully selecting a partner, the firm enters into the alliance. The performance evaluation of the alliance is conducted in order to assess the success of the alliance. Barriers to success, discussed in the benefits and limitations section, play a direct role in the determination of the performance of the alliance. The success of the alliance depends on how the barriers to success are handled by the partners. Firms that handle the barriers effectively are the ones that succeed in sustaining their alliance. Firms that do not succeed based on the performance evaluation have to assess the motives for alliance formation with an environmental analysis in order to detect any problems that went unnoticed the first time during the alliance formation.

The integrated model proposed by Sameer Vaidya adds to the current literature on strategic alliances by integrating the three approaches suggested by Kogut, the process model suggested by Osland and Yaprak, and the dimensions of strategic alliances model by Vetat. The two models and Kogut's approaches are complementary to each other and therefore

can be used in an integrated model like the one suggested. The addition of the partner selection criteria also adds a new dimension to the new model. Although the literature in strategic alliances does not pay enough attention to the selection criteria, it is one of the most important elements of forming a successful strategic alliance. It is important to note that performance is not described in this model in terms of specific variables because alliances define performance in different terms.

Benefits and Limitations of Strategic Alliances

Firms experience the benefits of the alliance when the alliance succeeds in achieving the goals or fulfilling the needs of the partners. The benefits of strategic alliances are derived from the motives for formation of strategic alliances. Lower cost of technology, sharing of risk in high-risk projects, ability to accrue economies of scale and scope in value-added activities, access to partner's technology, knowledge, and proprietary processes, and basis for future competition in the industry involved in terms of sustained competitive advantage are all benefits of strategic alliances which were previously mentioned as motives for alliance formation. Successful alliances are between firms that achieve their goals and the motives for formation of the alliance. Management decides to enter into an alliance after conducting an internal & external environmental analysis and finding discrepancies in their goals. These discrepancies are filled with capabilities of other firms by forming an alliance. These capabilities are termed as motives before the alliance is

formed and benefits after the alliance is successful.

Several limitations and drawbacks of alliance formation, however, may accompany the benefits of forming a strategic alliance. One of the greatest costs to a firm is the liquidation cost of the alliance, if the partners do not agree. Losing proprietary know-how is also considered to be a high impact drawback of forming alliances. Other potential drawbacks of forming strategic alliances are:

Control related problems: Strategy implementation usually goes beyond the control of one party, and thus is likely to bother some companies. Dependence on partners for skills is a potential drawback to one who is dependent.

Unequal gains: Some partners in the alliance may gain more than other which can cause problems for the partner getting less out of the alliance.

Differences in cultural values: Corporations encompassing different cultures may experience culture clashes after the formation of the alliance. **Role ambiguity:** Uncertainty about specific roles may limit organizations from fulfilling their obligations to the alliance.

Partner's alliance with competing firms: A partner may establish cooperative linkages with competing firms, which may hamper the present alliance.

Facing antitrust charges: Antitrust regulations can restrict the benefits of an alliance with a

major partner and invite governmental intervention.

These disadvantages contribute to the failure of strategic alliances. Although the disadvantages seem to outnumber the advantages mentioned in this section, mutual gains from alliances can outweigh disadvantages. For the alliance to be successful, firms should possess a change-oriented corporate culture, along with continuous mutual commitment and support. Firms that possess culture that allows and encourages change are usually successful in forming strategic alliances. The change-oriented culture allows the worker to handle the barriers to success effectively in order to reduce failure of the alliance.

CONCLUSIONS

Strategic alliances represent a medium that can create scale and scope advantages necessary to be competitive on a global basis. Alliances allow firms to conserve their resources as compared to forming a wholly owned subsidiary. Strategic alliances also allow firms to gain local identity giving them an advantage over wholly owned subsidiaries when dealing with local governments and businesses. The above statements discuss the gains of forming an alliance. Yet there are disadvantages to forming alliances rather than wholly owned subsidiaries. The advantages and disadvantages of alliances have to be carefully weighed by each organization before making a decision to enter an alliance.

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